

* Encoding: UTF-8.

```
DATASET ACTIVATE DataSet1.  
FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=BeforeAfter  
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.
```

Frequencies

Statistics

Posted before or after Musk announcement

N	Valid	227
	Missing	0

Posted before or after Musk announcement

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Before	34	15.0	15.0	15.0
	After	193	85.0	85.0	100.0
	Total	227	100.0	100.0	

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Comments  
/STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV RANGE MIN MAX.
```

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of comments	227	3500	0	3500	76.22	340.970
Valid N (listwise)	227					

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Shares  
/STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV RANGE MIN MAX.
```

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of shares	227	10200	0	10200	236.28	910.267
Valid N (listwise)	227					

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=Likes
  /STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV RANGE MIN MAX.
```

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of likes	227	176370	30	176400	1881.49	12052.536
Valid N (listwise)	227					

```
DESCRIPTIVES VARIABLES=AFINNvalue
  /STATISTICS=MEAN STDDEV RANGE MIN MAX.
```

Descriptives

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
AFINN value	227	25	-9	16	.26	3.404
Valid N (listwise)	227					

```
T-TEST GROUPS=BeforeAfter(0 1)
  /MISSING=ANALYSIS
  /VARIABLES=Comments
  /CRITERIA=CI(.95).
```

T-Test

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of comments	Before	34	254.15	812.093
	After	193	44.88	130.016

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	Std. Error Mean
Number of comments	Before	139.273
	After	9.359

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality ..
		F	Sig.	t
Number of comments	Equal variances assumed	44.186	.000	3.375
	Equal variances not assumed			1.499

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Number of comments	Equal variances assumed	225	.001	209.266
	Equal variances not assumed	33.299	.143	209.266

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			Lower	Upper
Number of comments	Equal variances assumed	62.008	87.075	331.458
	Equal variances not assumed	139.587	-74.629	493.161

```
T-TEST GROUPS=BeforeAfter(0 1)
/MISSING=ANALYSIS
/VARIABLES=Shares
/CRITERIA=CI(.95).
```

T-Test

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of shares	Before	34	494.47	1774.291
	After	193	190.80	648.343

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	Std. Error Mean
Number of shares	Before	304.288
	After	46.669

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality ..
		F	Sig.	t
Number of shares	Equal variances assumed	10.694	.001	1.803
	Equal variances not assumed			.986

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Number of shares	Equal variances assumed	225	.073	303.673
	Equal variances not assumed	34.567	.331	303.673

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			Lower	Upper
Number of shares	Equal variances assumed	168.466	-28.301	635.646
	Equal variances not assumed	307.846	-321.569	928.914

T-TEST GROUPS=BeforeAfter(0 1)

/MISSING=ANALYSIS
/VARIABLES=Likes
/CRITERIA=CI(.95).

T-Test

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Number of likes	Before	34	7058.71	30281.698
	After	193	969.44	2792.597

Group Statistics

	Posted before or after Musk announcement	Std. Error Mean
Number of likes	Before	5193.268
	After	201.016

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality ..
		F	Sig.	t
Number of likes	Equal variances assumed	24.900	.000	2.756
	Equal variances not assumed			1.172

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Number of likes	Equal variances assumed	225	.006	6089.265
	Equal variances not assumed	33.099	.250	6089.265

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
			Lower	Upper
Number of likes	Equal variances assumed	2209.674	1734.963	10443.568
	Equal variances not assumed	5197.157	-4483.230	16661.761

```
T-TEST GROUPS=BeforeAfter(0 1)
/MISSING=ANALYSIS
/VARIABLES=AFINNvalue
/CRITERIA=CI(.95).
```

T-Test

Group Statistics

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
AFINN value	Posted before or after Musk announcement Before	34	.12	2.910	.499
	After	193	.29	3.489	.251

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means	
		F	Sig.	t	df
AFINN value	Equal variances assumed	1.500	.222	-.272	225
	Equal variances not assumed			-.309	51.264

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
AFINN value	Equal variances assumed	.786	-.173	.634
	Equal variances not assumed	.759	-.173	.559

Independent Samples Test

		t-test for Equality of Means	
		95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		Lower	Upper
AFINN value	Equal variances assumed	-1.423	1.078
	Equal variances not assumed	-1.294	.949

CROSSTABS

```

/TABLES=Codes_ANH BY Codes_IS
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
/STATISTICS=KAPPA
/CELLS=COUNT
/COUNT ROUND CELL.
    
```

Crosstabs

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Codes ANH * Codes IS	227	100.0%	0	0.0%	227	100.0%

Codes ANH * Codes IS Crosstabulation

Count

		Codes IS			Total
		Information	Neutral	Misinformation	
Codes ANH	Information	7	3	1	11
	Neutral	6	202	5	213
	Misinformation	0	2	1	3
Total		13	207	7	227

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Measure of Agreement	Kappa	.469	.105	8.765	.000
N of Valid Cases		227			

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

```
FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=FINAL_CODE
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.
```

Frequencies

Statistics

Agreed code

N	Valid	Missing
	227	0

Agreed code

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Information	13	5.7	5.7	5.7
	Neutral	210	92.5	92.5	98.2
	Misinformation	4	1.8	1.8	100.0
	Total	227	100.0	100.0	

```
ONEWAY Comments BY FINAL_CODE
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
/PLOT MEANS
/MISSING ANALYSIS.
```

Oneway

Descriptives

Number of comments

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence ... Lower Bound
Information	13	68.77	185.603	51.477	-43.39
Neutral	210	77.96	351.635	24.265	30.12
Misinformation	4	9.50	6.455	3.227	-.77
Total	227	76.22	340.970	22.631	31.63

Descriptives

Number of comments

	95% Confidence Interval for ...		
	Upper Bound	Minimum	Maximum
Information	180.93	4	682
Neutral	125.79	0	3500
Misinformation	19.77	4	18
Total	120.82	0	3500

Means Plots

*Nonparametric Tests: Independent Samples.
NPTESTS

/INDEPENDENT TEST (Comments) GROUP (FINAL_CODE) KRUSKAL_WALLIS COMPARE=PA

```
IRWISE)
/MISSING SCOPE=ANALYSIS USERMISSING=EXCLUDE
/CRITERIA ALPHA=0.05 CILEVEL=95.
```

Nonparametric Tests

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Number of comments is the same across categories of Agreed code.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.805	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

```
ONEWAY Shares BY FINAL_CODE
/STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
/PLOT MEANS
/MISSING ANALYSIS.
```

Oneway

Descriptives

Number of shares

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for ... Lower Bound
Information	13	146.46	321.702	89.224	-47.94
Neutral	210	246.00	942.619	65.047	117.76
Misinformation	4	18.25	16.049	8.025	-7.29
Total	227	236.28	910.267	60.417	117.23

Descriptives

Number of shares

	95% Confidence Interval for ... Upper Bound	Minimum	Maximum
Information	340.86	5	1100
Neutral	374.23	0	10200
Misinformation	43.79	8	42
Total	355.33	0	10200

Means Plots

*Nonparametric Tests: Independent Samples.

NPTESTS

/INDEPENDENT TEST (Shares) GROUP (FINAL_CODE) KRUSKAL_WALLIS(COMPARE=PAIRWISE)

/MISSING SCOPE=ANALYSIS USERMISSING=EXCLUDE

/CRITERIA ALPHA=.05 CILEVEL=95.

Nonparametric Tests

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Number of shares is the same across categories of Agreed code.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.598	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

```

ONEWAY Likes BY FINAL_CODE
  /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
  /PLOT MEANS
  /MISSING ANALYSIS.

```

Oneway

Descriptives

Number of likes

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for ... Lower Bound
Information	13	824.00	1721.904	477.570	-216.54
Neutral	210	1980.41	12520.803	864.017	277.11
Misinformation	4	124.75	95.339	47.670	-26.96
Total	227	1881.49	12052.536	799.955	305.16

Descriptives

Number of likes

	95% Confidence Interval for ...		
	Upper Bound	Minimum	Maximum
Information	1864.54	37	4800
Neutral	3683.72	30	176400
Misinformation	276.46	30	257
Total	3457.81	30	176400

Means Plots


```

*Nonparametric Tests: Independent Samples.
NPTESTS
  /INDEPENDENT TEST (Likes) GROUP (FINAL_CODE) KRUSKAL_WALLIS(COMPARE=PAIRWISE)
  /MISSING SCOPE=ANALYSIS USERMISSING=EXCLUDE
  /CRITERIA ALPHA=0.05 CILEVEL=95.

```

Nonparametric Tests

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of Number of likes is the same across categories of Agreed code.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.264	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.

```

ONEWAY AFINNvalue BY FINAL_CODE
  /STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVES
  /PLOT MEANS
  /MISSING ANALYSIS.

```

Oneway

Descriptives

AFINN value					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence ... Lower Bound
Information	13	-1.46	2.876	.798	-3.20
Neutral	210	.38	3.437	.237	-.09
Misinformation	4	.00	1.633	.816	-2.60
Total	227	.26	3.404	.226	-.18

Descriptives

AFINN value

	95% Confidence Interval for ...		
	Upper Bound	Minimum	Maximum
Information	.28	- 6	4
Neutral	.84	- 9	16
Misinformation	2.60	- 2	2
Total	.71	- 9	16

Means Plots

*Nonparametric Tests: Independent Samples.
NPTESTS
/INDEPENDENT TEST (AFINNvalue) GROUP (FINAL_CODE) KRUSKAL_WALLIS(COMPARE=
PAIRWISE)
/MISSING SCOPE=ANALYSIS USERMISSING=EXCLUDE
/CRITERIA ALPHA=0.05 CILEVEL=95.

Nonparametric Tests

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The distribution of AFINN value is the same across categories of Agreed code.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	.209	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.